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J. Indian Chem. Soc.,
Vol. LI, December 1974, pp. 1049-1050

Action of Some Colloids on Corrosion of 3S Aluminium in Trichloroacetic Acid

S. S. SAMPAT, R. M. OZA and J. C. VORA

Chemistry Department, University School of Sciences, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-9.

Manuscript received 17 October 1973 ; accepted 1 July 1974

THE colloids are known since long for their inhibitive power¹⁻⁶. Colloids have been studied as inhibitor for iron⁷⁻⁸, copper⁹, brass¹⁰⁻¹² in different acid media. Ramachar et al. used dextrin and tannin as inhibitors for corrosion of aluminium and its alloys in hydrochloric acid¹³⁻²¹. However, very little work has been reported on the inhibition of aluminium by substituted acetic acid. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the inhibitive power of some colloids towards the corrosion of 3S aluminium in trichloroacetic acid solutions.

Experimental :

Aluminium alloy used had the following composition : Mn 1-1.5, Fe-0.7, Cu-0.15, Si-0.6, and Zn-0.1%. For determining loss in weight, specimen of the size 3×6 cm. were immersed in 250 ml of 1.0 and 0.5 M trichloroacetic acid solutions. The methods employed for the preparation of specimens, corrosion testing and cleaning of the specimen were those reported by Champion²². The coupons used for galvanostatic studies had an effective area 4 sq. cm. (size 2×2 cm), the length of the handle being 4 cm. The handle and the back of the coupons and of the auxiliary electrode were coated with perspex and wax. Experiments were carried out at 35°±2°. The concentration of the inhibitors used was that at which maximum inhibition was observed.

The results of weight loss and polarization are given in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. The original weight of the specimen was approximately 3.5 g. The loss of weight in 0.1M trichloroacetic acid at 5 and 10 days durations were 598 and 744 mg respectively while in 0.5 M trichloroacetic acid for 15 and 24 hrs durations, the weight loss were 1640 and 2250 mg. respectively.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Results and Discussion :

The weight loss data show that the colloids gave excellent inhibition in 0.5M trichloroacetic acid. The inhibition efficiency decreased somewhat with decrease in concentration and the duration. The colloids can be arranged accordingly to their decreasing inhibitive power as follows: gelatine > tannin > casein > dextrin. Colloids like gelatine, tannin etc. have been extensively studied for their electric charges and stabilities. Colloids form a continuous insulating adsorbed layer on the metal surface²²⁻²⁴. It is this layer which appears to be responsible for inhibition exhibited by them. Further the layer appears too thin to be seen visually. The polarization data reveal that it is the cathode which is principally polarized. Isoelectric point of gelatine, a lyophilic sol, is at pH 4.7, and change of pH will cause a sharp increase in its viscosity, since the particles then carry charge²⁵. In the present investigation the pH values of 0.1 and 0.5M trichloroacetic acid solutions were 1.3 and 0.7 respectively. At pH below 4.4 gelatine will carry a positive charge. These charged species can migrate towards cathode; reaching the cathode, the lyophilic sol will be discharged and coagulate at the surface, thus blocking the cathodic sites.

Acknowledgement :

Our thanks are due to late Prof. A. M. Trivedi for ever inspiring guidance and C.S.I.R. for generous grant and a fellowship to one of us (SSS).

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